

STATE OF SHEEP BREEDING AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS**Rizayeva D.T.**

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of sheep breeding in the national economy, its current state, development prospects, the number of sheep in the world and in our country, as well as the implementation of increasing production in sheep breeding and improving quality. manufactured products, analyzed the work done, and gave appropriate conclusions and recommendations.

Key words: Livestock breeding, sheep breeding, horse population, food products, productivity, productivity, sheep breeds, Jaidari, Hisar, Karakol, raw materials, meat, wool, leather.

Introduction.

Sheep farming is considered one of the oldest and most important branches of livestock farming and has played an important role in the economic and social life of human society for centuries. It was considered an important source of food and income for the population.

Sheep are the most numerous of domestic animals and are distributed in all regions of the earth.

Sheep farming plays an important role in providing the population with high-quality food, including meat and meat products, as well as providing industrial sectors with high-quality raw materials, such as wool, fur and astrakhan skins.

In recent years, the sharp increase in the number of people on earth has caused an increase in demand for food. Therefore, the development of sheep breeding, increasing the number of sheep and increasing their productivity is of scientific and practical importance.

If you pay attention, in subsequent years special importance is attached to the development of sheep farming in Uzbekistan. On March 16, 2019, adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures for further development and support of the livestock industry” No. ZP-4243, on March 28, 2019 “Veterinary Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZP-4254”,

dated May 20, 2019 No. Z-538 "On pastures" dated February 8, 2022, Decision ZP-120 on the approval of the Program for the Development of Livestock Husbandry and Its Industries in the Republic for 2022-2026 is a clear example of this. These laws and regulations are aimed at increasing the number and productivity of livestock, including sheep, in our republic and are of great importance in the development of the industry.

If we pay attention to the dynamics of the existing sheep population in countries around the world and in our country, we can witness positive changes in the coming years.

Table 1

**Number of sheep in countries with developed sheep farming, million.
(according to FAO)**

Countries	Years		
	2010	2015	2018
Australia	68,1	70,9	70,1
China	134,0	158,5	164,1
New Zealand	32,6	29,1	27,3
India	67,7	62,2	61,7
Iran	47,6	44,7	39,7
Great Britain	31,1	33,3	33,8
Turkiye	21,8	31,1	33,7
South Africa	24,5	23,9	22,5
Pakistan	27,7	29,4	30,5
Russia	19,8	22,6	22,3
Ukraine	1,20	0,79	0,73
Kazakhstan	14,66	15,69	16,42
Kyrgyzstan	4,09	5,06	5,36
Azerbaijan	7,87	8,02	7,68
Tajikistan	2,62	3,36	3,67
Uzbekistan	12,08	15,20	17,77
Turkmenistan	13,60	14,00	14,07

According to the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the global sheep population was 1076400000 in 2010, 1176900000 in 2015 and 1209500000 in 2018. We can

observe that this figure increased in 2018 by 2.77% compared to 2015 and by 12.36% compared to 2010.

Today, the leaders in sheep numbers are countries such as China, Australia, India, Nigeria, Sudan, Great Britain, Iran, Ethiopia, Chad, and Turkey. These countries account for 4/3 of the products produced in the industry.

Sheep farming is more economically efficient than other livestock sectors. Availability of storage on pastures for up to 11 months throughout the year allows you to save costs on production. Currently, there are about 24 million sheep and goats in our country, and the bulk of the meat produced comes from this industry. In our republic, the number of sheep per 100 people is 65.

According to the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of January 1, 2023, the total number of sheep and goats raised in our republic increased to 23,602.5 thousand heads. We see that this figure has increased by 53.85% in 2023 compared to 2011.

Table 2

Information on the number of sheep in Uzbekistan.

Regions	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
The Republic of Uzbekistan	15340,9	16189	17128,8	17717,6	18438,9	19118,8	19697,9	20640,9	21580,5	21906,9	22458,8	22970,3	23602,5
Republic of Karakalpagistan	764,3	802,7	838,6	873,3	876,9	901,5	939,7	1031,8	1089,7	1115,1	1142,6	1178,5	1213,9
Andijan region	890,5	970,9	1176,1	1188	1213,6	1224	1290,5	1365,1	1434,9	1437,2	1450,6	1491,1	1526,6
Bukhara region	1563,2	1631,9	1703	1760,6	1825,1	1936,7	2043,4	2068,2	2115,9	2189,1	2239,8	2304	2416,5
Jizzakh region	1363,8	1440,4	1538	1552	1659,7	1727,4	1823	2006,9	2118,3	2155,7	2216,3	2255,2	2320,7
Kashkadarya region	3233,5	3511,1	3819,8	3954,4	4116,5	4281,5	4412,6	4518,4	4599,2	4614,2	4727,1	4784	4898,6
Navai Region	1745,8	1796,5	1706,8	1731,8	1782,6	1869	1834	1875	2091,8	2151,4	2254,8	2321,3	2378,8
Namangan region	614,2	628	647,7	661,6	679,2	696	702,4	716	765,1	767,6	782,6	803,1	824,8
Samarkand region	1647,6	1722	1827	1940,9	2074,2	2150,7	2205,8	2282,8	2397,1	2434,2	2488,3	2546,3	2607,4
Surkhandarya region	1701	1768,6	1847,4	1926,2	1978,9	2024,1	2089,7	2234,1	2316,9	2361,4	2420,9	2479,2	2536,1
Sirdarya region	191,8	207,6	224,2	244,1	258,9	278	293,5	320	347,6	347,7	348,9	362,8	378,5
Region Tashkent	645	684,2	723,9	758,7	786	820	836,2	968,2	1017,6	1033,2	1061	1071,9	1086,3
Fergana region	624,8	665,5	706,8	747,7	799,1	811,5	829,2	831,8	851,4	856,7	870,5	893,2	917,8
Khorezm region	355,4	359,6	369,5	378,3	379,9	389,8	396	415,4	428,2	436,5	448,4	471,2	484,6
Tashkent city	0	0	0	0	8,3	8,6	1,9	7,2	6,8	6,9	7	8,5	11,9

Table 3

Information on the number of sheep in Uzbekistan (percentage of total sheep population).

Regions	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
The Republic of Uzbekistan	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Republic of Karakalpagistan	4,98	4,96	4,9	4,93	4,76	4,72	4,77	5	5,05	5,09	5,09	5,13	5,14
Andijan region	5,8	6	6,87	6,71	6,58	6,4	6,55	6,61	6,65	6,56	6,46	6,49	6,47
Bukhara region	10,19	10,08	9,94	9,94	9,9	10,13	10,37	10,02	9,8	9,99	9,97	10,03	10,24
Jizzakh region	8,89	8,9	8,98	8,76	9	9,04	9,25	9,72	9,82	9,84	9,87	9,82	9,83
Kashkadarya region	21,08	21,69	22,3	22,32	22,33	22,39	22,4	21,89	21,31	21,06	21,05	20,83	20,75
Navai Region	11,38	11,1	9,96	9,77	9,67	9,78	9,31	9,08	9,69	9,82	10,04	10,11	10,08
Namangan region	4	3,88	3,78	3,73	3,68	3,64	3,57	3,47	3,55	3,5	3,48	3,5	3,49
Samarkand region	10,74	10,64	10,67	10,95	11,25	11,25	11,2	11,06	11,11	11,11	11,08	11,09	11,05
Surkhandarya region	11,09	10,92	10,79	10,87	10,73	10,59	10,61	10,82	10,74	10,78	10,78	10,79	10,75
Sirdarya region	1,25	1,28	1,31	1,38	1,4	1,45	1,49	1,55	1,61	1,59	1,55	1,58	1,6
Region Tashkent	4,2	4,23	4,23	4,28	4,26	4,29	4,25	4,69	4,72	4,72	4,72	4,67	4,6
Fergana region	4,07	4,11	4,13	4,22	4,33	4,24	4,21	4,03	3,95	3,91	3,88	3,89	3,89
Khorezm region	2,32	2,22	2,16	2,14	2,06	2,04	2,01	2,01	1,98	1,99	2	2,05	2,05
Tashkent city	0	0	0	0	0,05	0,04	0,01	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,04	0,05

Today in our country there is a favorable opportunity for the development of sheep breeding. Existing conditions, food supply, natural pastures in specialized farms of different forms of ownership make it possible to increase the number of existing sheep several times and increase the amount of products produced.

For this: strengthening the fodder base of sheep farming and increasing the potential of fodder production, efficient use of land allocated for nutritious crops and existing pastures, systematic creation of nutritious crops, preventing desertification processes in existing pastures and increasing their productivity, increasing the number of nutritious sown areas, increasing the yield of nutritious crops, increasing food supply the value of nutrients, properly organize the conservation and storage of nutrients accumulated as a reserve, increase the production of natural and cheap live food. organization of breeding work in sheep breeding on a scientific basis, improvement of sheep breeds in all categories of farms, systematic implementation of artificial insemination;

integration of production with science and organization of cooperation between farms, breeding farms and research institutes at the demand level;

increase productivity by improving the quality of keeping and caring for sheep, correctly designing buildings and structures, ensuring compliance with zoohygienic standards and microclimate indicators in sheepfolds at the required level;

- proper organization of prevention and treatment of infectious and invasive diseases;

- increase the number of sheep in specialized farms;

- transfer of production processes to a complete technological system;

introduction of new innovative technologies into the field;

stimulation of production. Distribution of tax benefits and subsidies;

- introduction of a preferential lending system;

- attracting domestic and foreign investment for the development of sheep farming;

creating a favorable business environment in the field;

Material and moral support for sheep breeding workers allows us to increase production volumes. This is important to ensure food safety.

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